

A4

A FAIR-enabling citation model for Cultural Heritage Objects

Schema Extension Development

UNIVERSITÀ
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CENTRO DI ATENEO
PER LE BIBLIOTECHE

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A4 / Schema Extension Development

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Abstract

Metadata is key to framing the context of the research data and can sometimes be part of the research data itself. The Metadata Standards Catalog (MSC), maintained by the RDA Metadata Standards Catalog Working Group, hosts more than one hundred descriptions of metadata standards, along with tools, mappings, and organisations that aim to help researchers choose the most suitable metadata standard to describe research data belonging to projects, repositories and catalogues.

In the context of the Cultural Heritage domain, we examined the consistency and evaluated the MSC subject domains with a view to enriching the Catalog with the metadata standards widely used by the Cultural Heritage research community. In addition, we investigated whether the MSC could play a role in guiding researchers to include relevant citation information in their project metadata, disciplinary metadata and dataset metadata, thereby fostering cross-disciplinary information integration while proving, at the same time, how citation can act as a FAIR-enabling factor.

Version history

Version	Date	Authors/Contributors	Description
V1.0	28/07/2023	Cristiana Bettella, Mauro Apostolico, Linda Cappellato, Yuri Carrer, Achille Felicetti, Giulio Turetta	

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Cover image: Gino Morandi (Morandis), Fresco at the entrance of Morgagni Hall at the University of Padua Hospital (detail). © 1964 Gino Morandi / © 2023 University of Padua.

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List of Abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
CH	Cultural Heritage
CHO	Cultural Heritage Object
CIDOC CRM	CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model
DRI	Digital Repository of Ireland
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
IG	Interest Group
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
MSC	Metadata Standards Catalog
RDA	Research Data Alliance
SIG	Special Interest Group
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
WG	Working Group

1 Introduction

In the process of evaluating and developing a context-sensitive schema extension to the Metadata Standards Catalog (MSC) of the RDA Metadata Standards Catalog Working Group, both in terms of content coverage and functionality, to document the citation of cultural heritage objects in native and non-native contexts, two main lines of study have been followed:

- A4.1 / Cultural Heritage domain assessment of the RDA Metadata Standards Catalog. Subject domains play an important role when it comes to choosing the metadata standard that suits better research data in that domain. As highlighted in the Catalog scope, metadata is key to framing the context of the research data and sometimes can be part of the research data itself. Considering the inherent cross-disciplinarity of cultural heritage objects, investigating consistency and assessing the Catalog subject domains supports the process of enhancing the Catalog with the metadata standards widely used by the Cultural Heritage research community.
- A4.2 / The RDA Metadata Standards Catalog as a home for citations practices: a proposal. Adding citation-specific fields to the description of the metadata standards in the RDA Metadata Standards Catalog, and studying metadata standards in non-CH subject domains to describe how citation-specific fields are included in the metadata standards.

As one of the objectives of the project is to propose the enrichment of the MSC data model from the dual point of view of catalogue coverage, in terms of descriptors and data models of the Cultural Heritage domain, and also as a proposal for the extension of the catalogue itself to integrate citation models in relation to metadata schemas, we have presented our project hypothesis to the MSC WG chairs. Both proposals, outlined in this document, were provisionally shared with the MSC WG chairs as soon as they were finalised.

2 Cultural Heritage domain assessment of the RDA Metadata Standards Catalog

This section outlines the evaluation of the RDA Metadata Standards Catalog for the Cultural Heritage domain, analyses the MSC subject domains for Cultural Heritage and the associated metadata standards, and suggests enhancements to the Catalog.

2.1 Rationale

The Research Data Alliance Metadata Standards Catalog is a collaborative, open directory of metadata standards applicable to research data.

The Catalog states its focus is on “metadata standards that may be used to document research data, but this simple statement hides a large amount of complexity”. Moreover, “as explained in the RDA Metadata Principles, the distinction between metadata and data depends on the context, since ‘metadata’ really describes a role that a particular set of data plays in a given process”¹.

Subject domains play an important role when it comes to choosing the metadata standard that better suits research data in a given domain. As highlighted in the Catalog scope, metadata is key to framing the context of the research data and sometimes can be part of the research data itself. Considering the inner cross-disciplinarity of cultural heritage objects, investigating the consistency and assessing the Catalog subject domains supports the process of enhancing the Catalog with the metadata standards widely used by the cultural heritage research community.

2.2 Methodology

The Catalog adopts concepts from the UNESCO Thesaurus² for the classification of metadata standards based on subject areas³. We assessed the existing terms in the Catalog to find subjects that apply to the cultural heritage domain, with the aim to enrich the Catalog by tagging subject domains and adding new metadata standards.

We identified a set of metadata standards along with their matching subject domains and the possible relationships between standards, mappings and organisations. Eventually, we came to the proposal to add the CIDOC CRM standard by filling in the fields of the Catalog “Add Metadata Standard” form.

¹ <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/scope>

² <https://vocabularies.unesco.org/>

³ <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/subject-index>

2.3 Suggested Catalog Enhancements

2.3.1 Subject domains

The following subject domains, related to the Cultural Heritage sector, could be populated with the proposed metadata standards.

Subject	Rationale
<p><i>Cultural heritage > Documentary heritage > Digital heritage</i></p> <p><i>Documentary heritage:</i> https://vocabularies.unesco.org/browser/thesaurus/en/page/concept2783</p> <p><i>Digital heritage:</i> https://vocabularies.unesco.org/browser/thesaurus/en/page/concept8030</p>	<p>Needed to represent the digital documentation of a cultural heritage object.</p> <p>This subject represents born-digital cultural heritage objects too.</p>
<p><i>Science > Scientific approach > Scientific methods</i></p> <p><i>Scientific approach:</i> http://vocabularies.unesco.org/thesaurus/mt2.05</p> <p><i>Scientific methods:</i> http://vocabularies.unesco.org/thesaurus/concept106</p>	<p>Needed for metadata standards aimed at collecting scientific data from Cultural Heritage objects. For example, the CRMsci metadata standard would be added to this subject (see below).</p>

Table 1: Proposed cultural heritage subject domains.

2.3.2 Metadata standards

We propose to add these metadata standards, already included in the Catalog, to the following subjects.

Metadata Standard	Subject	Rationale
LIDO (Lightweight Information Describing Objects)	<i>Cultural Heritage > Documentary Heritage > Digital Heritage</i>	The CIDOC CRM and its application profiles are increasingly being adopted for the digital representation of cultural heritage objects.
EAD (Encoded Archival Description)	<i>Information and communication > Documentary information systems > Archives</i>	Being a widely used metadata standard for archival records, it also describes the archives, their organisation, relationships, and entity management. It represents a way to collect research data from archives too.

Table 2: Proposed cultural heritage subject domains and metadata standards.

We propose the addition of the following metadata standards to the Catalog.

CIDOC CRM

CIDOC CRM is a conceptual model used in cultural heritage to enable information integration. It provides definitions and a structured framework to describe concepts, relationships, and data used in cultural heritage documentation. The CIDOC CRM, developed and maintained over a period of more than 20 years, was initially proposed by the CIDOC Documentation Standards Working Group and is currently managed by the CIDOC CRM SIG, both of which are working groups of the CIDOC Council. In December 2006, it received official recognition as an ISO standard, and this status was reaffirmed in 2014 under the ISO 21127:2014 designation.

CIDOC CRM is currently used by various museums and other cultural institutions, such as the British Museum, for modelling their cultural information. It has also been employed in numerous international initiatives focused on the integration and interoperability of cultural heritage data, including ARIADNE and ARIADNEplus⁴, MINGEI⁵, PARTHENOS⁶, and 4CH⁷.

⁴ <https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu>

⁵ <https://www.mingei-project.eu>

⁶ <https://www.parthenos-project.eu>

⁷ <https://www.4ch-project.eu>

CIDOC CRM also comes with a series of extensions that have been developed over the years for modelling data in many different research domains. These extensions address specialised areas of investigation and are tailored to support different types of research questions, being crafted in partnership with the relevant research communities. CIDOC CRM and its extensions provide a powerful ecosystem and a large number of conceptual tools to model in advanced semantic form events, objects, people, time and places according to the significance these elements acquire in different disciplines.

Documentation: <https://www.cidoc-crm.org/>

Add to:

- *Cultural Heritage*
- *Historical Studies*
- *Archaeology*
- *Museums*
- *Libraries*
- *Archives*

The following standards are some of the most relevant CIDOC CRM extensions.

CRMsci

CRMsci is the extension for scientific observation and is specifically designed to support the documentation and integration of scientific data.

It provides a structured framework for capturing and describing scientific observations, measurements, and experiments in various domains such as environmental studies, natural sciences, and biodiversity research.

Documentation: <https://cidoc-crm.org/crmsci/>

Add to:

- *Cultural Heritage*
- *Scientific Methods*

CRMdig

CRMdig, for digital preservation, is an extension tailored for the domain of digital preservation. It provides a conceptual framework for documenting and managing the lifecycle of digital objects, ensuring their long-term preservation and accessibility.

CRMdig incorporates additional classes and relationships to capture the unique characteristics and requirements of digital preservation, including concepts such as file formats, metadata, migration, authenticity, and provenance.

It can be used to model and manage digital collections, establish preservation policies, and implement strategies for the sustainable preservation of digital materials.

Documentation: <https://www.cidoc-crm.org/crmdig/>

Add to:

- *Cultural Property Preservation*
- *Digital Heritage*

LRMoo

LRMoo, formerly known as FRBRoo, is an extension, developed in collaboration with IFLA, for bibliographic information and library cataloguing. It provides a conceptual framework for describing bibliographic entities and their relationships in a structured manner by introducing classes, properties, and relationships that allow for the representation of bibliographic resources, such as books, articles, and other library materials, along with their authors, editions, and related works.

LRMoo facilitates the organisation and retrieval of bibliographic information by providing a consistent and standardised approach to cataloguing. It enables the modelling of complex relationships between different versions, translations, and editions of a work, as well as the association of works with their creators and subjects.

Documentation: <https://www.cidoc-crm.org/frbroo/ModelVersion/version-0.9.3>

Add to:

- *Information/library standards*

CRMarchaeo

CRMarchaeo is an extension designed to address the documentation and management of archaeological data and excavation processes. CRMarchaeo expands upon the CIDOC CRM base ontology by introducing additional classes, properties, and relationships that enable the representation of archaeological entities and their contextual information.

It also provides a structured framework for capturing and describing archaeological sites, artefacts, stratigraphy, excavation processes, and related archaeological concepts.

It supports the documentation of archaeological contexts, including the spatial and temporal dimensions of excavations, stratigraphic relationships, and the association of artefacts with specific layers or features.

Documentation: <https://www.cidoc-crm.org/crmarchaeo/>

Add to:

- *Archaeology*

CRMtex

CRMtex is the extension defined to address the documentation and representation of text-related cultural heritage objects. It provides a structured framework for describing various types of textual objects, including inscriptions, papyri, manuscripts, and other ancient texts. It aims to facilitate the organisation and retrieval of text-related cultural heritage objects by providing a standardised approach to their documentation and description.

CRMtex allows cultural heritage institutions, libraries, and research projects to manage and share textual resources effectively. It also enhances the interoperability of text-related data, enabling the integration of textual information from diverse sources, to facilitate scholarly research, textual analysis, and the preservation of textual cultural entities for future generations.

Documentation: <https://www.cidoc-crm.org/crmtex/>

Add to:

- *Cultural Heritage*
- *Linguistics*

TEI/EPIDOC

TEI/EPIDOC is a collaborative effort that combines the expertise of EpiDoc and the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI). It establishes standardised guidelines and tools for encoding scholarly and educational editions of ancient documents, embracing inscriptions, papyri, manuscripts, and other text-bearing objects. By leveraging a subset of TEI's standard, TEI/EPIDOC enables the representation of texts in a digital form while also addressing the historical context and materiality of the objects.

This comprehensive approach allows scholars to publish digital editions that not only encompass the transcription and editorial treatment of the texts but also provide insights into the objects

themselves. As a result, TEI/EPIDOC enriches our understanding of ancient civilizations and facilitates the dissemination of knowledge about their tangible heritage.

TEI/EPIDOC is currently employed by the EAGLE Project⁸ and Epigraphy.info⁹.

Documentation: <https://epidoc.stoa.org/>, <https://github.com/EpiDoc>

Add to:

- *Archaeology*
- *History*
- *Linguistics*
- *Cultural Heritage*

We suggest further investigation into the addition of the following standards.

Europeana Data Model (EDM)

Description: <https://bartoc.org/en/node/17946>

Documentation: <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/edm-documentation>

Add to:

- *Digital Heritage*

BIBFRAME

Initiated by the Library of Congress, BIBFRAME provides a foundation for the future of bibliographic description, both on the web and in the broader networked world grounded in Linked Data techniques. A significant focus of the initiative is to determine a transition path for the MARC 21 formats while preserving a robust data exchange that has supported resource sharing and cataloguing cost savings in recent decades.

Documentation: <https://www.loc.gov/bibframe/>

Add to:

- *Bibliographic standards*

⁸ <https://www.eagle-network.eu/>

⁹ <https://epigraphy.info/>

Linked Art Data Model

It is a CIDOC CRM application profile.

Documentation: <https://linked.art/model/>,
<https://cidoc.mini.icom.museum/working-groups/linked-art/>

Add to:

- *Arts and humanities*
- *Cultural Heritage*
- *Visual arts*
- *Museums*

LRMer (IFLA Library Reference Model Entity Relationship)

Documentation: <https://www.iflstandards.info/lrm/lrmer>

Add to:

- *Libraries*
- *Bibliographic services*

2.3.3 Relationships

We suggest adding the following relationships.

- Add LIDO (Lightweight Information Describing Objects) as an application profile of CIDOC CRM. LIDO uses the concepts and structure defined by CIDOC CRM, adapting them to a simplified and more practical format for metadata delivery purposes. It was the CIDOC CRM event-centric modelling that inspired LIDO to introduce an Event element in addition to elements taken from CDWA Lite. Some of the CIDOC CRM classes and their definitions were considered in or aligned with the LIDO Terminology, particularly terms for the *<lido:category>* and *<lido:eventType>* elements. A mapping between LIDO 1.0 and the CIDOC CRM version 6.0¹⁰ has been prepared in 2017, using the X3ML¹¹ mapping definition language.
- Add the CIDOC CRM extensions described above as application profiles of CIDOC CRM metadata standard.

2.3.4 Mappings

We propose adding the following mappings/crosswalks to the Catalog. The mappings described below are a selection of the mappings available on the CIDOC CRM "Reports about mappings" web page¹².

LIDO to CIDOC CRM

Description

A mapping between LIDO v1.0 and CIDOC-CRM v6.0.

Links and documentation

- <https://cidoc-crm.org/Resources/mappings-between-lido-v1.0-and-cidoc-crm-v6.0-in-x3ml-ver.1>

Responsible people and organizations

- Maintainer: [CIDOC - ICOM International Committee for Documentation](#)
- Creator: Lida Charami, Martin Doerr

Identifiers

Not available

¹⁰ <https://cidoc-crm.org/Resources/mappings-between-lido-v1.0-and-cidoc-crm-v6.0-in-x3ml-ver.1>

¹¹ <https://www.ics.forth.gr/isl/x3ml-toolkit>

¹² https://www.cidoc-crm.org/reports_mappings

Version history

Not available

MIDAS-Heritage to CIDOC CRM

Description

A mapping from MIDAS-Heritage to CIDOC CRM.

Links and documentation

- [MIDAS mapping](#)
- [MIDAS mapping notes](#)

Responsible people and organizations

- Maintainer: [ICOM International Committee for Documentation](#)
- Creator: not available

Identifiers

Not available

Version history

Not available

Dublin Core to CIDOC CRM

Description

The document describes the mapping of the DC-types to the CIDOC CRM version 4.2.2. It's a Technical Report for DELOS WP5-Task 5.5. "Ontology Driven Interoperability", January 2007.

The mapping of the DC-types to the CIDOC CRM version 4.2.2. was also presented at C. Kakali, I. Lourdi, T. Stasinopoulou, L. Bountouri, C. Papatheodorou, M. Doerr, M. Gergatsoulis, "Integrating Dublin Core Metadata for Cultural Heritage Collections Using Ontologies, Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Dublin Core and Metadata Applications, DC-2007, Singapore, August 2007, pp. 128-139. This paper also presents a mapping from the Dublin Core Collection Application Profile (DCCAP) to CRM.

The document describes the mapping of the Dublin Core Element set to the CIDOC CRM version 2.3 and the Agios Pavlos extensions.

Links and documentation

- [DC.type mapping to CIDOC/CRM](#)
- [Mapping of the Dublin Metadata to the CIDOC CRM.pdf](#)
- [Mapping of the Dublin Metadata to the CIDOC CRM.rtf](#)

Responsible people and organizations

- Maintainer: [CIDOC - ICOM International Committee for Documentation](#)
- Creator: Christos Papatheodorou, Konstantia Kakali, Martin Doerr, Thomais Stasinopoulo

Identifiers

Not available

Version history

- 2007-01-26: version 2007 <[DC.type mapping to CIDOC/CRM](#)>
- 2000-07: version 2000 <[Mapping of the Dublin Metadata to the CIDOC CRM.pdf](#)>

EAD to CIDOC CRM

Description

Mapping of the EAD to the CIDOC CRM version 4.2.2.

Described in the technical report of DELOS WP5-Task 5.5 "Ontology Driven Interoperability".

Links and documentation

- [EAD mapping to CIDOC/CRM](#)
- [Mapping of the encoded Archival Description DTD Element Set to the CIDOC CRM.pdf](#)
- [Mapping of the encoded Archival Description DTD Element Set to the CIDOC CRM.rtf](#)

Responsible people and organizations

- Maintainer: [CIDOC - ICOM International Committee for Documentation](#)
- Creator: Thomais Stasinopoulou, Martin Doerr, Konstantia Kakali, Lina Bountouri, Irene Lourdi, Christos Papatheodorou, Martin Doerr, Manolis Gergatsoulis

Identifiers

Not available

Version history

Not available

MARC to CIDOC CRM

Description

A mapping from the UNIMARC Bibliographic format (2nd edition Update 4 2002) to the semantic model CIDOC CRM (version 4.0 April 2004).

Links and documentation

- [Mapping from UNIMARC Bibliographic to CIDOC CRM](#)

Responsible people and organizations

- Maintainer: [CIDOC - ICOM International Committee for Documentation](#)
- Creator: Patrick Le Bœuf

Identifiers

Not available

Version history

Not available

2.3.5 "Add Metadata Standard" Form

We propose the following values to be entered in the fields of the "Add Metadata Standard" form to add the CIDOC CRM metadata standard to the Catalog (Figure 1).

CIDOC CRM

Name of metadata scheme

CIDOC CRM

Description

CIDOC CRM is a conceptual model used in cultural heritage to enable information integration. It provides definitions and a structured framework to describe concepts, relationships, and data used in cultural heritage documentation. The CIDOC CRM, developed and maintained over a period of more than 20 years, was initially proposed by the CIDOC Documentation Standards Working Group and is currently managed by the CIDOC CRM SIG, both of which are working groups of the CIDOC Council. In December 2006, it received official recognition as an ISO standard, and this status was reaffirmed in 2014 under the ISO 21127:2014 designation.

Subject areas

- Cultural Heritage
- Historical Studies
- Archaeology
- Museums
- Libraries
- Archives

Types of data described by this scheme

Dataset

Relevant links

- <https://cidoc-crm.org/> [website]

- <https://www.cidoc-crm.org/versions-of-the-cidoc-crm> [specification document]

Unversioned predicate namespaces for this scheme

- Prefix: crm
- URL: <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/>

Identifiers for this scheme

Not available.

Relationships to other records

- Parent metadata schemes
 - Not applicable
- Profiles of this scheme
 - LIDO
 - CIDOC CRM extensions we proposed to add

Mappings that take this scheme as input

Not available.

Mappings that give this scheme as output

- MIDAS-Heritage to CIDOC CRM
- Dublin Core to CIDOC CRM
- EAD to CIDOC CRM
- MARC to CIDOC CRM
- LIDO to CIDOC CRM

Organizations that maintain this scheme

CIDOC - ICOM International Committee for Documentation <<https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/msc/g130>>

Organizations that funded this scheme

CIDOC - ICOM International Committee for Documentation <<https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/msc/g130>>

Organizations that use this scheme

- British Museum <<https://www.britishmuseum.org/>>
- ARIADNE RI <<https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu>>
- MINGEI <<https://www.mingei-project.eu>>
- PARTHENOS <<https://www.parthenos-project.eu>>
- 4CH <<https://www.4ch-project.eu>>
- Arches <<https://www.archesproject.org>>
- Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cluster (SSHOC) <<https://sshopencloud.eu/>>
- IPERION HS <<https://www.iperionhs.eu/>>
- The National Gallery <<https://www.nationalgallery.org.uk/>>

Tools that support this scheme

- X3ML Mapping Tool <<https://www.ics.forth.gr/isl/x3ml-toolkit>>
- FastCat <<https://github.com/isl/FastCat>>, <<https://isl.ics.forth.gr/FastCatTeam>>
- ARIADNE Portal <<https://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>>

Endorsements of this scheme

Not defined.

Edit metadata scheme msc:m114

Name of metadata scheme

CIDOC CRM

Description

CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CRM) is a conceptual model used in cultural heritage to enable information integration. It provides definitions and a structured framework to describe

Subject areas

Cultural heritage < Cultural policy and planning < Arts and humanities

Historical studies < Arts and humanities

Archaeology < Historical studies < Arts and humanities

Museums < Arts and humanities

Libraries < Documentary information systems < Information and communication

Archives < Documentary information systems < Information and communication

Fig. 1. Metadata editing in the RDA Metadata Standards Catalog.

2.4 Submission

The draft of this document was reviewed by Alex Ball – RDA Metadata Standards Catalog Working Group³³, whom we thank for the valuable feedback.

We then inserted the CIDOC CRM and its extensions as new metadata standards in the Catalog (Figure 2). We also added the related organisations, crosswalks, and tools (25-07-2023).

We also inserted the TEI/EPIDOC metadata standard (26-07-2023).

The submitted Catalog records will be reviewed by members of the RDA Metadata Standards Catalog Working Group.

The screenshot shows the RDA Metadata Standards Catalog interface. At the top, there is a dark red navigation bar with the text "Metadata Standards Catalog" on the left and "Search", "My profile", and "Sign out" on the right. Below this, the main heading "CIDOC CRM" is displayed in a large, dark font. A paragraph of text describes the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CRM) as a conceptual model used in cultural heritage to enable information integration, developed and maintained over more than 20 years, and recognized as an ISO standard in 2006 and reaffirmed in 2014. Below the text, there are two sections: "Used in" and "Used for". The "Used in" section contains five brown buttons: "Cultural heritage", "Historical studies", "Archaeology", "Museums", and "Libraries". The "Used for" section contains one yellow button: "Dataset". At the bottom of the page, the heading "Documentation" is visible, followed by two horizontal blue lines.

Fig. 2. CIDOC CRM standard as displayed in the RDA Metadata Standards Catalog.

³³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/metadata-standards-catalog-working-group.html>

3 RDA Metadata Standards Catalog schema extension

This section describes a proposal for how the RDA Metadata Standards Catalog can play a role in guiding researchers to include relevant citation information in their project metadata, disciplinary metadata and dataset metadata, thereby fostering cross-disciplinary information integration while proving, at the same time, how citation can act as a FAIR-enabling factor.

3.1 Rationale

Evaluate the addition of citation-specific fields to the metadata standards description in the RDA Metadata Standards Catalog (MSC).

Citation is relevant to the resource metadata, as highlighted by the RDA Metadata IG¹⁴. Typically, data citation can be exposed by the data repository or the digital context of the resource. Project activity A2 pointed out that registries of research data repositories, such as re3data.org¹⁵, can include a metadata element to pinpoint the data citation policy of the research data repository.

Citation of cultural heritage objects allows the creation of a network of related works on them, thereby strengthening cross-disciplinary information integration.

The RDA MSC collects metadata standards described by its own scheme consisting of several fields¹⁶. We investigated whether the Catalog metadata standard fields can play a role in directing researchers to include relevant citation information in their project metadata, disciplinary metadata and dataset metadata, focusing on CHO citations in cross-disciplinary domains, such as the research domains that coalesce under the umbrella of so-called Heritage Science, in order to demonstrate the FAIR-enabling function performed by citation.

3.2 Methodology

In order to enable the citation of cultural heritage objects, we attempted to find out how non-CH metadata standards can represent the information needed to cite the CHO.

We then investigated metadata schemas with a focus on disciplinary contexts (subject domains) that don't belong to the Cultural Heritage domain, but that can be used to explore CHOs in a non-native context.

¹⁴ See: Citations, s.v. Metadata element set: <http://bit.ly/2nDH5Lr>. The current topic that the Metadata Interest Group (MIG) <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/metadata-ig.html> is working on the definition of the metadata element set intended to become a RDA Recommendation. See: Recommended Metadata Element Set: <http://bit.ly/2nDH5Lr>, and also the presentation by Keith G. Jeffery, *The Metadata Groups Unpacking the Elements*, held at "Metadata at P16 Virtual Costa Rica" (2020) <https://www.rd-alliance.org/metadata-p16-virtual-costa-rica>.

¹⁵ <https://www.re3data.org/>

¹⁶ Metadata Standards Catalog WG Final Report

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/metadata-standards-catalog-wg/outcomes/metadata-standards-catalog-wg-final-report>

The Catalog analysis has been performed on a number of metadata standards, focusing on metadata schemas of Chemistry and Botany. This was also due to the cross-disciplinary characterisation that both disciplines have with the CH domain, in line with the case studies analysed as exploratory interviews in the context of the project activity A2.

3.3 Findings and Discussion

As a detailed analysis of all Catalog metadata standards is beyond the scope of the project analysis, we decided to focus on metadata standards with non-CH subject domains that already adopt the citation as part of the data model, such as the GBIF metadata standard¹⁷.

As further evidence, we can think of citation as the common ground that interconnects “things”, i.e. the need to identify and provide information that allows the “thing” to be found. From this perspective, citation can be seen as

- part of the data model (metadata schemas, applied ontologies)
- part of the hosting context (repositories “Cite as” feature, museum record cards, library catalogues)
- used to refer to the “thing” itself.

This last role of the citation can be found mainly on “things” with a strong cultural background, such as Cultural Heritage Objects.

3.3.1 Citation as part of the data model

Especially in scientific metadata schemas, the resources that are the subject of the study are not easy to identify, or may not be mentioned at all. For example, a dataset collecting axial tomography data or chemical analyses rarely cites the CHO that is the subject of the study.

The GBIF metadata standard provides detailed guidelines for data citation¹⁸, including extensive examples¹⁹ and descriptions²⁰.

“This more consistent, standardized approach has now enabled us to auto-generate all text citations for datasets”, states the GBIF FAQs, and “encourage consistent citation of data use”²¹. This clearly

¹⁷ <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/msc/m61>

¹⁸ <https://www.gbif.org/citation-guidelines>

¹⁹ <https://www.gbif.org/faq?q=citation>

²⁰ Lane, M. (2008), *Data citation in the electronic environment*, a white paper commissioned by GBIF. Copenhagen: Global Biodiversity Information Facility. Available online at <http://www.gbif.org/document/80798>

²¹ “Where does the dataset citation text come from? I published this dataset, and that is not the citation text that I provided!” <https://www.gbif.org/faq?q=citation>

demonstrates the approach of including citation in the metadata of datasets. The citation FAQs also documents the critical citation elements²².

In the previous section, we proposed the addition to the Catalog of several ontologies, meant as metadata schemas, linked to the Cultural Heritage domain. For these metadata schemas, it could be possible to document the citation model (when available).

In the context of the Catalog, we propose to add the “Citation Documentation” property to the metadata standard descriptors to emphasise the support for citation in the metadata standard. Moreover, to strengthen the FAIR-enabling specifications of the cultural heritage objects citation, we propose to use the “Citation Documentation” property to describe how to cite resources such as CHOs as a further refinement.

Data repositories may also have citation policies, so we propose to add a “Citation Documentation” property to organisations to be filled in when applicable.

As a prototype implementation of this proposal, we forked²³ the RDA Metadata Standards Catalog source code available on GitHub, and we implemented the aforementioned field.

Figure 3 and 4 below depict the GBIF metadata standard and the DRI²⁴ organisation record with the “Citation Documentation” property filled in.

²² “How is the dataset citation text auto-generated?” <https://www.gbif.org/faq?q=citation>

²³ <https://github.com/yurj/metadata-catalog-v2>

²⁴ Digital Repository Ireland (DRI) <https://dri.ie/>. DRI has been selected as a case study along with Archaeology Data Service (ADS) <https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/> and Phaidra - University of Padua <https://phaidra.cab.unipd.it>. The results are discussed in project output A3 / CHO Citation Elements Repository Case Studies.

GBIF Metadata Profile

Established by a global network of countries and organizations, GBIF is a web portal promoting and facilitating the mobilization, access, discovery and use of biodiversity data. The portal uses a profile of EML; a [How-to Guide](#) and [Reference Guide](#) for using the profile are available.

Used in [Biogeography](#) [Biological diversity](#) [Botany](#) [Ecology](#) [Zoology](#)

Documentation

[Visit website](#)

Citation Documentation

The GBIF metadata standard provides [in-depth guidelines](#) on data citation, [with extensive examples](#) and description ("[Data citation in the electronic environment - a white paper commissioned by GBIF](#)")

[FAQs](#) "How is the dataset citation text auto-generated?" and "Where does the dataset citation text come from? I published this dataset, and that is not the citation text that I provided!" explain how citation are included in metadata and what are the critical citation elements.

GBIF provide an [EML](#) reference to the [format of the citation](#).

Identifiers

Internal MSC ID [msc:m61](#)

Version history

2016-10-25	version 1.1 (current)	View specification in XSD format	Edit version
2015-02-13	version 1.0.2	View specification in XSD format	Edit version

Relationships to other metadata standards

- This scheme is a profile of [EML \(Ecological Metadata Language\)](#).

[Edit this record](#)[Add another version](#)

Fig. 3. GBIF metadata schema with the "Citation Documentation" property filled in.

Digital Repository of Ireland

Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI) is a national trusted digital repository (TDR) for Ireland's social and cultural data. It supports records catalogued in Dublin Core, EAD, MARC XML and MODS.

Organization type archive

Links and documentation

Visit website

Citation Documentation

Dri has a citation policy (Dublin Core) <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.rx91h486p> which endorse data citation recommendations such as CODATA-ICSTI "Task Group on Data Citation Standards and Practices, Out of Cite, Out of Mind: The Current State of Practice, Policy, and Technology for the Citation of Data" https://www.jstage.jst.go.jp/article/dsj/12/0/12_OSOM13-043/_pdf and "UK Data Archive, Data Citation. What you need to know" http://ukdataservice.ac.uk/media/104397/data_citation_online.pdf

Related metadata standards

- This organization uses [Dublin Core](#), [EAD \(Encoded Archival Description\)](#), [MARC \(Machine-Readable Cataloging\)](#) and [MODS \(Metadata Object Description Schema\)](#).

Identifiers

Internal MSC ID [msc:g121](#)

Edit this record

Fig. 4. DRI organisation with the "Citation Documentation" property filled in.

The source code implementing the proposed feature can be found in the GitHub commit <https://github.com/yurj/metadata-catalog-v2/commit/57bbcd169ee8a074231d8214a3213d7coacfad>.

3.4 Future developments

The idea of citation and its critical elements to be included in the metadata schema suggests that we can improve the CHO's citation by using this additional information. Below, we highlight a section of the GBIF Metadata Profile related to citation and an example of GBIF metadata that includes citation.

The following is a section of the GBIF Metadata Profile related to citation²⁵:

```
<xs:element name="additionalMetadata">
  <xs:annotation>
  <xs:documentation>
  A flexible field for including any other relevant metadata that pertains to the resource being
  described. This field allows EML to be extensible in that any XML-based metadata can be included
  in this element.
  </xs:documentation>
  </xs:annotation>
  <xs:complexType>
  <xs:sequence>
  <xs:element name="metadata">
  <xs:annotation>
  <xs:documentation>
  This element contains the additional metadata to be included in the document. This element
  should be used for extending EML to include metadata that is not already available in another
  part of the EML specification.
  </xs:documentation>
  </xs:annotation>
  <xs:complexType>
  <xs:sequence>
  <xs:element name="gbif">
  <xs:annotation>
  <xs:documentation>
  A block of additional metadata used for some special GBIF purposes and crossmapping to other
  schemas like the TDWG Natural Collection Data (NCD) schema
  </xs:documentation>
  </xs:annotation>
  <xs:complexType>
  <xs:sequence>
  <!-- additional general metadata -->
  <xs:element name="dateStamp" type="xs:dateTime">
  <xs:annotation>
```

²⁵ <http://rs.gbif.org/schema/eml-gbif-profile/1.2/eml-gbif-profile.xsd>

```

<xs:documentation>
The date the metadata document was created or modified.
</xs:documentation>
</xs:annotation>
</xs:element>
<xs:element name="hierarchyLevel" type="NonEmptyStringType" minOccurs="0">
<xs:annotation>
<xs:documentation/>
</xs:annotation>
</xs:element>
<xs:element name="citation" type="citationType" minOccurs="0">
<xs:annotation>
<xs:documentation>A single citation for use when citing the dataset</xs:documentation>
</xs:annotation>
</xs:element>
<xs:element name="bibliography" minOccurs="0">
<xs:annotation>
<xs:documentation>
A list of citations that form a bibliography on literature related / used in the dataset
</xs:documentation>
</xs:annotation>
<xs:complexType>
<xs:sequence>
<xs:element name="citation" type="citationType" maxOccurs="unbounded"/>
</xs:sequence>
</xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
[...]
```

The following is an example of GBIF metadata related to citation²⁶:

```

<additionalMetadata>
<metadata>
<gbif>
<dateStamp>2023-07-26T09:04:12Z</dateStamp>
<citation>
AFFOUARD A, JOLY A, LOMBARDO J, CHAMP J, GOEAU H, CHOUET M, GRESSE H, BOTELLA C,
BONNET P (2023). PI@ntNet automatically identified occurrences. Version 1.8. PI@ntNet.
Occurrence dataset https://doi.org/10.15468/mma2ec accessed via GBIF.org on 2023-07-26.
</citation>
<bibliography>
<citation identifier="https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2013.07.006">
Joly, A., Goëau, H., Bonnet, P., Bakić, V., Barbe, J., Selmi, S., ... & Yahiaoui I., Carré J., Mouysset E.,
Molino J.-f., Boujemaa B., Barthélémy D., (2014). Interactive plant identification based on social
image data. Ecological Informatics, 23, 22-34.
```

²⁶ <https://api.gbif.org/v1/dataset/14d5676a-2c54-4f94-9023-1e8dcd822aao/document>

```
</citation>
<citation identifier="https://doi.org/10.1007/s00530-015-0462-9">
Joly, A., Bonnet, P., Goëau, H., Barbe, J., Selmi, S., Champ, J., Dufour-Kowalski, S., Affouard, A.,
Carré, J., Molino, J.-f., Boujemaa, N., & Barthélémy D., (2016). A look inside the PI@ntNet
experience. Multimedia Systems, 22(6), 751-766.
</citation>
<citation identifier="https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01629183">
Goëau, H., Bonnet, P., Joly, A., 2017. Plant identification based on noisy web data: the amazing
performance of deep learning (LifeCLEF 2017). CLEF: Conference and Labs of the Evaluation
Forum, Sep 2017, Dublin, Ireland. <hal-01629183>
</citation>
<citation identifier="https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01629195">
Affouard, A., Goëau, H., Bonnet, P., Lombardo, J. C., & Joly, A., (2017). PI@ntNet app in the era of
deep learning. ICLR: International Conference on Learning Representations, Apr 2017, Toulon,
France. <hal-01629195>
</citation>
</bibliography>
<resourceLogoUrl>https://api.plantnet.org/public/plantnet.jpeg</resourceLogoUrl>
</gbif>
</metadata>
</additionalMetadata>
```

As this example suggests, once the citation field is part of a metadata standard, this field can contain the CHO citation. Furthermore, the current citation can be extended to include properties derived from a CHO citation model²⁷.

²⁷ A CHO can be properly cited using a citation analysis approach as discussed in the project output A3 / CHO Citation Elements. Repository Case Studies.